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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AARCHA SURESH 9SU21NS001** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISREE K V 9SU21NS002** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA A 9SU21NS003** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AIRIN WILLY 9SU21NS004** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AISWARYA KRISHNAN K has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISWARYA RADHAKRISHNAN C M** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AJANYA A 9SU21NS007** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHINA GOPI G 9SU21NS008** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAYA P P 9SU21NS009** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEENA ANTO 9SU21NS010** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEENA RAJ V K 9SU21NS011** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEENA S 9SU21NS012** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALEENA SUSAN MATHEW** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMRUTHA ANIL 9SU21NS014** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANAMIKA K 9SU21NS015** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANCY MOL S 9SU21NS016** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANEENA JOSEPH 9SU21NS017** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANGEL MARY THOMAS** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJALI P S 9SU21NS019 has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJANA VENU 9SU21NS020 has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANNA GRACE 9SU21NS021 has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANNMARIA MATHEW 9SU21NS022** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **APARNA K 9SU21NS023** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA K 9SU21NS024** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA RAVINDRAN 9SU21NS025** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHNITHA JOSE 9SU21NS026** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASRITHA P 9SU21NS027** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWANI A 9SU21NS028** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWANI O K 9SU21NS029** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASWATHI SANDEEP P 9SU21NS030** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHIRA K V 9SU21NS031** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHUL P P 9SU21NS032** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVANTHIKA MAHESH 9SU21NS033** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYISHA AFRA 9SU21NS034** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BLESSY K B 9SU21NS035** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAITHRA 9SU21NS036** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHANDINI A 9SU21NS037** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CINDRELLA BEN MATHEW** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DISNA PAUL 9SU21NS039** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAIRUSA JABEEN 9SU21NS040** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FEBA JAYAMON 9SU21NS041** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FESNA T A 9SU21NS042** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIYAT V S 9SU21NS043** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISMAYA P 9SU21NS044** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOBIN JOHNY 9SU21NS045** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOTHIS THOMAS 9SU21NS046** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA T V 9SU21NS047** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA NARAYANAN K V** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KERAN SARA SABU 9SU21NS049** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEZIA SARA THOMAS 9SU21NS050** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNAPRIYA K V 9SU21NS051** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAKSHMI SANTHOSH 9SU21NS052** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LIYAMOL JACOB 9SU21NS053** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LIYANA SHERIN 9SU21NS054** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEENAKSHI R 9SU21NS055** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEGHA VIJAYAN 9SU21NS056** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MELBA MARTIN 9SU21NS057** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MURSHIDA NESRIN E N** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA PAVITHRAN** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA S 9SU21NS060** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDANA SATHYAN 9SU21NS061** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIVEDYA RAJU C 9SU21NS062** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIYA SANDRIYA PANAGADAN** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PARVATHEE KRISHNA U S** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAISE ANNA BABU 9SU21NS065** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRIYA M 9SU21NS066** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAISA K 9SU21NS067 has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAWAN 9SU21NS068** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RESHNA P V 9SU21NS069** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROSE MARIYA RAJU 9SU21NS070** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROSHNA B L 9SU21NS071** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RUDRA PRIYA V S 9SU21NS072** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAFA FATHIMA B S 9SU21NS073** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHYA V N 9SU21NS074** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA BINOY 9SU21NS075 has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDRA JOSEPH 9SU21NS076** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANGEETHA RENJI 9SU21NS077** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANIYA NAZEER 9SU21NS078** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJANA T V 9SU21NS079** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANKEERTH K 9SU21NS080** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHANA SHERIN P T 9SU21NS081** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIVA NANDA 9SU21NS082** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRUTHI V 9SU21NS083** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA ANIMON 9SU21NS084** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA CHANDRASEKHAR M** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA K 9SU21NS086** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SONA EBBY 9SU21NS087** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SONA SAJI 9SU21NS088** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREE LAKSHMI DAS K 9SU21NS089** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHANA SHEREEF K 9SU21NS090** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURYA A B 9SU21NS091** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THANVI 9SU21NS092** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA VARGHESE 9SU21NS093** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YADHUKRISHNA K 9SU21NS094** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ISHWARYA 9SU21NS095** has completed his/her minor project on **“Knowledge regarding hospital acquired infection among staff nurses”** in the first year BSc Nursing programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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